

Annex 1.1. Business and biodiversity – Indigenous and local knowledge methods

The assessment followed the IPBES approach to recognizing and working with Indigenous and local knowledge,¹ informed by the IPBES methodological guidance on recognizing and working with Indigenous and local knowledge,² and supported by the IPBES task force and technical support unit on Indigenous and local knowledge.

The work with Indigenous and local knowledge included a group of twenty authors, including co-chairs, coordinating lead authors and lead authors, forming an “Indigenous and local knowledge liaison group” tasked with working on Indigenous and local knowledge in the assessment, including developing cross-chapter narratives.

Two dialogue workshops took place during the assessment cycle, in addition to an online dialogue in 2021 for the scoping of the assessment. These dialogues brought together members of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs) and assessment authors to discuss key themes, concepts, progress, gaps and ways forward for the assessment. A first dialogue for framing the assessment and discussing key themes and questions took place in Bogota, Colombia over 23 and 24 September 2023. A second dialogue for reviewing the draft assessment and summary for policymakers took place at the !Khwatla San Cultural Centre near Cape Town, South Africa over 31 July to 2 August 2024. Reports were prepared from both workshops and were used as resources by the assessment authors.³

The workshops applied the principle of free, prior and informed consent, including sharing the reports with participants before publishing them for comments or approval. The second dialogue workshop for the assessment also presented an opportunity for members of IPLCs to review the draft chapters and summary for policymakers, as part of the overarching cycle of free, prior and informed consent practised by IPBES assessments.

The assessment's approach also included extensive review of literature and materials, including peer-reviewed articles, Indigenous community reports, and other materials. These materials were enhanced by a call for contributions on Indigenous and local knowledge for the assessment, which received 225 submissions.

Contributing authors, including Indigenous Peoples and dialogue workshop participants, were also invited to submit portions of text relating to Indigenous and local knowledge, to further enhance the expertise and knowledge presented by the assessment.

The review period of the assessment also provided an opportunity for members of IPLCs and others with experience working with Indigenous and local knowledge to provide comments and suggest ways forward for the assessment, further adding to the knowledge and experience included in the assessment process.

¹ Available here: https://files.ipbes.net/ipbes-web-prod-public-files/inline/files/ipbes_ilkapproach_ipbes-5-15.pdf

² Available here: https://files.ipbes.net/ipbes-web-prod-public-files/inline-files/IPBES_ILK_MethGuide_MEP-Approved_5MAY2022.pdf

³ The dialogue workshop reports are available here: <https://www.ipbes.net/ilk-dialogue-reports>

Annex 1 Figure 1. Aligning Business Success with Respect for People, IPLCs, and Nature.

Annex 1.2. Sectoral classification according to the ISIC typology

For the purposes of this assessment, International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) “section” and “division” (level 2 division codes) are used as the primary typological unit for sector. For example, fishing and aquaculture are defined by section and division code A03.⁴ Higher levels of aggregation occasionally used in the related scholarly and grey literatures, such as classifications like “resource extraction and cultivation”, “resource conversion and manufacturing”, “services” and “consumption” –or– “primary industry”, “secondary industry” and “tertiary industry” can be ambiguous. To maximize generality, when possible, this assessment avoids the use of more specific subsector definitions including 3-digit code sector “groups” or 4-digit “classes”. Some diversified entities may have multiple ISIC classifications. Elsewhere in this assessment, references to businesses operating in each sector may practically refer to a subset or division of a diversified larger business.

The financial sector is included in the business typology under the ISIC system, including insurance, reinsurance and pension funds and activities that support financial services (UN, 2008).

The typology of business size used in this assessment defines the following categories: micro: <5 participants, including sole traders; small: 5-50 participants; medium: 51-500 participants; and large: >500 participants, noting that there is no universally agreed upon typology of business size. For practical implementation, we define participant numbers above based on full-time equivalence engaging in relevant business activities. Defining business size on the basis of participants allows the assessment to remain inclusive of entities operating at micro and small scales, where common metrics like revenues, employees or sales may be difficult to systematically track, assess, and quantify. Small and medium-sized enterprises regularly have important impacts and dependencies on nature and nature's contribution to people (TNFD, 2023). Examples of micro-scale activities with significant dependencies and impacts may include the local-level use of non-timber forest products (e.g., beekeeping, mushroom collection, medicinal plants), community-based tourism activities, small scale energy production from firewood and charcoal, and small-scale fishing.

⁴ Sectors previously defined as having consistently high impact or high dependence on biodiversity are well captured by these 2 levels of aggregation: Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities (A01); forestry and logging (A02); fishing and aquaculture (A03); mining and quarrying (B04-B09); manufacturing, including food, beverages, tobacco, textiles, apparel, paper, chemicals, rubber and plastics, and basic metals (C10-C33); electricity generation (D35); water supply, sewerage, waste management (E36-39); construction (F41-43); transportation and storage (H49-53); tourism (N79); and human health activities (Q86). Financial and insurance activities (K64-66) that may have impacts and dependencies on biodiversity are also captured by this system.

Annex 2, Table 1.1. Typology of business activity by size, region and sector using the ISIC classification system

Baseline typology of business				
By size:	Micro < 5 participants	Micro 6 - 50 participants	Medium 51- 500 participants	Big > 500 participants
By region:	Africa	The Americas	Asia and the pacific	Europe and Central Asia
By sector:	Description	Section		Division
	Agriculture, forestry, and fishing	A		01–03
	Mining and quarrying	B		05–09
	Manufacturing	C		10–33
	Electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply	D		35
	Water supply; sewage, waste management, and remediation activities	E		36–39
	Construction	F		41–43
	Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles	G		45–47
	Transportation and storage	H		49–53
	Accommodation and food service activities	I		55–56
	Information and communication	J		58–63
	Financial and insurance activities	K		64–66
	Real estate activities	L		68
	Professional, scientific, and technical activities	M		69–75
	Administrative and support service activities	N		77–82
	Public administration & defence; compulsory social security	O		84
	Education	P		85
	Human health and social work activities	Q		86–88
	Arts, entertainment, and recreation	R		90–93
	Other service activities	S		94–96
Activities of households as employers	T		97–98	

	Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies	U	99
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Annex 2 – References

TNFD. (2023). Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) Recommendations – TNFD. <https://tnfd.global/publication/recommendations-of-the-taskforce-on-nature-related-financial-disclosures/>

UN (Ed.). (2008). International Standard industrial classification of all economic activities (ISIC) (Rev. 4). United Nations.